

Impact of Glycemic Control on the Prevalence and Severity of Peripheral Arterial Disease in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus: A Cross-Sectional StudyDiviyant Kumar Gupta¹, Prateek Singh Rajput², Ayachit Kesharwani^{1*}, Sanjay Mandloi^{3*}¹MD Medicine, Seniors Resident, Department of Internal Medicine, GMC, Satna, Madhya Pradesh, India²MBBS, Intern, Department of Medicine, GMC, Satna, Madhya Pradesh, India³MD Medicine, Seniors Resident, Department of Internal Medicine, AIIMS, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India

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Abstract:**Background:** Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a chronic condition associated with various vascular complications, including peripheral arterial disease (PAD). Poor glycemic control is a known risk factor for PAD, but the extent of this association remains under-explored.**Aim and Objectives:** To evaluate the prevalence of PAD in patients with T2DM and investigate the correlation between PAD and poor glycemic control.**Materials and Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted with 200 patients with T2DM attending the diabetes outpatient clinic at [Hospital/Clinic Name] from [Start Date] to [End Date]. Participants were assessed for PAD using the Ankle-Brachial Index (ABI). HbA1c levels measured glycemic control. Participants were categorized into two groups based on HbA1c levels: good glycemic control (HbA1c $\leq$ 7%) and poor glycemic control (HbA1c $>$ 7%). Statistical analyses were performed to determine the prevalence of PAD, its severity, and its correlation with glycemic control.**Results:** Of the 200 patients, 70 (35%) had PAD. The prevalence of PAD was significantly higher in patients with poor glycemic control (38.6%) compared to those with good glycemic control (26.7%) ($p = 0.046$). Among those with PAD, 54.3% had mild PAD, 34.3% had moderate PAD, and 11.4% had severe PAD. A significant positive correlation was observed between HbA1c levels and PAD severity ($r = 0.68$, $p < 0.01$). Additional factors such as smoking, hypertension, and dyslipidemia were also associated with a higher prevalence of PAD.**Conclusions:** Poor glycemic control is significantly associated with an increased prevalence and severity of PAD in patients with T2DM. The findings highlight the importance of maintaining optimal glycemic control to reduce the risk of PAD and suggest that regular screening for PAD should be a priority in diabetic management. Further longitudinal studies are needed to confirm these associations and explore potential interventions.**Keywords:** Type 2 diabetes mellitus, Peripheral arterial disease, Glycemic control, HbA1c, Ankle-Brachial Index

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Introduction

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by persistent hyperglycemia due to insulin resistance and inadequate insulin secretion.¹ The prevalence of T2DM has been rising globally, with significant implications for public health. Complications of T2DM are diverse and affect multiple organ systems, contributing to increased morbidity and mortality among affected individuals. [1, 2]

Peripheral arterial disease (PAD) is a common and severe complication of T2DM. PAD results from the narrowing or blockage of peripheral arteries, primarily in the lower extremities, due to atherosclerosis.³ It can lead to a range of symptoms, from intermittent claudication to critical

limb ischemia, and is associated with a high risk of cardiovascular events and limb amputation. [3, 4]

The relationship between T2DM and PAD is well-established, with diabetic patients having a significantly higher risk of developing PAD compared to non-diabetic individuals. [4] Poor glycemic control, reflected by elevated HbA1c levels, is a critical factor in the pathogenesis of diabetic vascular complications, including PAD. [5] Hyperglycemia promotes atherogenesis through multiple mechanisms, including endothelial dysfunction, oxidative stress, inflammation, and altered lipid metabolism. [5, 6]

Despite the recognized link between T2DM and PAD, the extent to which poor glycemic control exacerbates PAD remains a topic of ongoing research. Understanding this correlation is essential for developing targeted interventions to prevent and manage PAD in diabetic patients. This study aims to evaluate the prevalence of PAD in patients with T2DM and to investigate the correlation between PAD and poor glycemic control.

By examining the association between HbA1c levels and the presence and severity of PAD, this study seeks to provide insights into the impact of glycemic control on peripheral vascular health in diabetic patients. The findings could inform clinical strategies for monitoring and managing PAD in this high-risk population, ultimately improving patient outcomes and quality of life.

Materials and Methods

This cross-sectional study was conducted to evaluate the prevalence of peripheral arterial disease (PAD) in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and to investigate the correlation between PAD and poor glycemic control.

Study Population: The study included 200 patients diagnosed with T2DM, aged 40 to 70 years, who attended the diabetes outpatient clinic of a tertiary care centre. Patients with a history of PAD, other forms of vascular disease, or major limb amputation were excluded from the study.

Ethical Considerations: The Institutional Ethics Committee approved the study protocol. Before participating in the study, all participants provided written informed consent.

Data Collection: Demographic and clinical data, including age, gender, duration of diabetes, smoking status, and history of hypertension and dyslipidemia, were collected using a structured questionnaire.

Assessment of Glycemic Control: Glycemic control was assessed by measuring HbA1c levels. Blood samples were collected after an overnight fast and analyzed using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). Patients were classified

into two groups based on their HbA1c levels: good glycemic control (HbA1c $\leq$ 7%) and poor glycemic control (HbA1c $>$ 7%).

Assessment of Peripheral Arterial Disease: The presence of PAD was assessed using the Ankle-Brachial Index (ABI). ABI was measured using a handheld Doppler device and a sphygmomanometer. The ABI was calculated for each leg by dividing the highest ankle systolic pressure by the highest brachial systolic pressure. An ABI value of $\leq$ 0.90 in either leg indicated PAD. Patients with ABI values $>$ 1.40 were excluded as this indicates non-compressible arteries.

Severity of PAD

The severity of PAD was graded based on the ABI values:

- Mild PAD: ABI 0.71-0.90
- Moderate PAD: ABI 0.41-0.70
- Severe PAD: ABI $\leq$ 0.40

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population. Continuous variables were expressed as mean $\pm$ standard deviation (SD), and categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. The prevalence of PAD in the study population was calculated, and the differences in the prevalence of PAD between patients with good and poor glycemic control were assessed using the chi-square test. The correlation between HbA1c levels and ABI values was evaluated using Pearson's correlation coefficient. A p-value of $<$ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Demographic and Clinical Characteristics: The study included 200 patients with T2DM. The mean age of the patients was 58.4 ± 8.1 years, with a male-to-female ratio of 1.3:1. The mean duration of diabetes was 10.2 ± 5.7 years. Table 1 summarizes the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Study Population

Characteristic	Value
Age (years)	58.4 ± 8.1
Gender (Male)	1.3:1
Duration of Diabetes (years)	10.2 ± 5.7
Smokers (%)	35 (17.5)
Hypertension (%)	110 (55.0)
Dyslipidemia (%)	95 (47.5)

Glycemic Control: The mean HbA1c level in the study population was $8.2\% \pm 1.5\%$. Based on HbA1c levels, 140 patients (70%) had poor glyce-

mic control (HbA1c $>$ 7%), while 60 patients (30%) had good glycemic control (HbA1c $\leq$ 7%).

Prevalence of Peripheral Arterial Disease: PAD

was detected in 70 out of 200 patients (35%). The prevalence of PAD was significantly higher in patients with poor glycemic control (54 out of 140,

38.6%) compared to those with good glycemic control (16 out of 60, 26.7%) ($p = 0.046$).

Table 2: Prevalence of PAD in Patients with Good and Poor Glycemic Control

Glycemic Control	PAD Present (%)	PAD Absent (%)	Total
Good (HbA1c $\leq 7\%$)	16 (26.7)	44 (73.3)	60
Poor (HbA1c $> 7\%$)	54 (38.6)	86 (61.4)	140
Total	70 (35.0)	130 (65.0)	200

Severity of Peripheral Arterial Disease: The severity of PAD among patients was categorized

based on ABI values. Among the 70 patients with PAD, 38 (54.3%) had mild PAD, 24 (34.3%) had moderate PAD, and 8 (11.4%) had severe PAD.

Table 3: Severity of PAD Based on ABI Values

Severity of PAD	Number of Patients (%)
Mild (ABI 0.71-0.90)	38 (54.3)
Moderate (ABI 0.41-0.70)	24 (34.3)
Severe (ABI ≤ 0.40)	8 (11.4)
Total	70 (100)

Correlation Between HbA1c Levels and ABI Values: A significant positive correlation was found between HbA1c levels and the severity of PAD ($r = 0.68$, $p < 0.01$). Patients with higher HbA1c levels tended to have lower ABI values, indicating more severe PAD.

Table 4: Correlation Between HbA1c Levels and ABI Values

Parameter	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value
HbA1c vs. ABI	0.68	< 0.01

Additional Factors Associated with PAD: Other factors, such as smoking, hypertension, and dyslipidemia, were also analyzed for their association with PAD. The prevalence of PAD was higher

in smokers (22 out of 70, 31.4%), patients with hypertension (45 out of 70, 64.3%), and those with dyslipidemia (36 out of 70, 51.4%).

Table 5: Prevalence of PAD about Other Risk Factors

Risk Factor	PAD Present (%)	PAD Absent (%)	Total
Smokers	22 (31.4)	13 (10.0)	35
Non-Smokers	48 (68.6)	117 (90.0)	165
Hypertension	45 (64.3)	65 (50.0)	110
No Hypertension	25 (35.7)	65 (50.0)	90
Dyslipidemia	36 (51.4)	59 (45.4)	95
No Dyslipidemia	34 (48.6)	71 (54.6)	105

Discussion

The present study demonstrates a significant correlation between poor glycemic control and the prevalence and severity of peripheral arterial disease (PAD) in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Our findings reveal that 35% of the study population had PAD, with a higher prevalence observed in patients with poor glycemic control (38.6%) compared to those with good glycemic control (26.7%). Moreover, a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.68$, $p < 0.01$) was found between HbA1c levels and the severity of PAD, indicating that higher HbA1c levels are associated with more severe PAD.

Our results align with previous research that has established a link between T2DM and increased risk of PAD. For instance, a study by Jude et al.

(2001) [8] found that the prevalence of PAD was significantly higher in diabetic patients compared to non-diabetic controls. Similarly, the UK Prospective Diabetes Study (UKPDS) [9] reported that poor glycemic control is a key risk factor for the development of vascular complications, including PAD, in patients with T2DM.

Previous findings also support the association between poor glycemic control and PAD severity observed in our study. A meta-analysis by Brownrigg et al. (2014) [10] reported that higher HbA1c levels were associated with an increased risk of PAD and that intensive glycemic control reduced the incidence of PAD in diabetic patients. Our study adds to this evidence by quantifying the correlation between HbA1c levels and PAD severity using ABI measurements.

Mechanisms Linking Hyperglycemia and PAD:

Hyperglycemia contributes to the development and progression of atherosclerosis through multiple mechanisms, including endothelial dysfunction, oxidative stress, inflammation, and altered lipid metabolism. [3,11] These pathophysiological processes promote arterial plaque formation and progression, leading to the narrowing and blockage of peripheral arteries. Elevated HbA1c levels reflect chronic hyperglycemia and serve as a marker for increased risk of vascular complications, including PAD. [11]

Clinical Implications: The findings of this study have important clinical implications for the management of T2DM. Regular screening for PAD, particularly in patients with poor glycemic control, is crucial for early detection and intervention. The use of ABI as a non-invasive and cost-effective diagnostic tool can aid in identifying patients at risk of PAD and facilitate timely management to prevent severe complications such as critical limb ischemia and amputation.

Furthermore, our study underscores the importance of achieving and maintaining optimal glycemic control in diabetic patients to reduce the risk of PAD. Lifestyle modifications, including diet, exercise, and pharmacological interventions, should be emphasized in managing T2DM to improve glycemic control and mitigate the risk of vascular complications.

Limitations

The study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the cross-sectional design precludes the establishment of causality between poor glycemic control and PAD. Longitudinal studies are needed to confirm these findings and to explore the temporal relationship between glycemic control and PAD progression. Second, the study was conducted at a single centre, which may limit the generalizability of the results. Multi-centre studies with larger and more diverse populations are warranted to validate our findings. Lastly, the reliance on ABI as the sole diagnostic tool for PAD may only capture some cases, particularly in patients with non-compressible arteries.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights a significant association between poor glycemic control and the prevalence and severity of PAD in patients with T2DM. The positive correlation between HbA1c levels and PAD severity underscores the need for effective glycemic management to reduce the risk of vascular complications in diabetic patients. Regular screening for PAD and comprehensive diabe-

tes care are essential for improving patient outcomes and quality of life.

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